

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BRANDING, PACKAGING AND CONSUMERS' CHOICE OF SOFT DRINKS IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA.

Ogbuke John Chukwudi (Ph.D.), Prof. Nebo Gerald Nwora, Okafor Ozoemena Christian (Ph.D.), Ogbuke George Tochukwu, Barr. Ogbuke Julius, Dr. Eze Jude Obinna, , Prof. Innocent Ikenna Chukwu and Prof. Ngozi Grace Ejionueme

Department of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology,

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14170818>

ABSTRACT:	KEYWORDS
<p>The study examined the relationship between branding, packaging and consumers' choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria". The specific objectives were to: ascertain the relationship between branding on consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State, Nigeria and explore the relationship between packaging and consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study adopted the survey research design. The sample size of the study was three hundred and eight four (384). The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. The study hypotheses were tested using correlation methods. The findings showed that: branding had a positive significant relationship on consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria ($r=.520$, $pv = .000 < 0.05$) and packaging had a positive significant relationship on consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria ($r=.420$, $pv = .000 < 0.05$). Based on findings, the study concluded that branding and packaging had a positive significant relationship on consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria. Based on findings, the study recommended that manufacturers of soft drinks should ensure that their brands have good image, quality, value for money and identity within the market and soft drinks manufacturers should ensure that packaging materials, colours, designs, sizes and printed information are good.</p>	<p>Branding, Packaging, Consumer choice, soft drinks</p>

INTRODUCTION

Consumers' buying choice are heavily affected by the branding and packaging information descriptions in today's global, multifaceted, and culturally diverse marketplace. Researching branding and packaging is important for understanding how product differentiation might affect sales to consumers' choice of products like soft drinks. Not to mention, consumer choice is a pivotal and mediating factor in shaping consumers' purchasing habits. Alternatively, it is expected that there will be more demand for things that are branded and packaged than the going rate (Appu, *et al*, 2024).

The branding and packaging design of consumer goods plays an increasingly critical role in influencing purchasing decisions from view point of consumers, particularly in the context of the highly competitive soft

drinks products market. This study focuses on the Eastern region of Nigeria, specifically Enugu State metropolis, where soft drink is a significant part of the local economy. In this region, where soft drink practices are deeply embedded in the cultural fabric, packaging is more than just a container for products; it serves as a powerful tool for attracting consumer attention, conveying product quality, and influencing buying behavior (Tu, Khairun, & Nisa, 2024).

Understanding the impact of branding and packaging design on consumer choices is vital for several reasons. First, as consumers become more discerning and their reliance on visual and tactile cues grows, the effectiveness of branding and packaging in communicating value and quality cannot be overstated. In a marketplace flooded with options, the design of a product's branding and packaging can be the deciding factor that sets it apart from competitors, both local and international. This is particularly relevant in soft drinks, where maintaining the market appeal of quality products is essential for sustaining the region's health wise (Tu, Khairun, & Nisa, 2024).

Moreover, the study explores how branding and packaging can reflect the consumers' choice and authenticity of soft drinks products, aligning them with consumer expectations in a region that values tradition. This alignment is not only important for attracting local consumers but also for positioning these products in broader markets, where cultural resonance can be a unique selling point. Based on this backdrop, the paper seeks to investigate the relationship between branding, packaging and consumers' choice of soft drinks in Enugu metropolis.

Statement of the Problem

In the competitive business world, packaging and branding are essential. They assist businesses in making a lasting impression on customers and standing out among their target market. They must ensure that it conveys a renewed vision and mandate, thus businesses must choose appropriate packaging because it raises the perceived value of products. Effective packaging influences consumers' choices by considering the product's quality in addition to its design. In the end, it provides customers with an experience they won't forget.

Through this research, valuable insights will be gained into the standing and exposure of various companies' brands in the marketplace, shedding light on the true potency of branding and packaging compared to their competitors. By studying the competitive market, this research aims to uncover the profound effects of packaging and branding on the marketing productivity of products.

Branding and packaging is a very important aspect of product marketing strategy that helps to attract the consumer's attention. Consumers nowadays are bombarded with too many marketing stimuli and clues by different companies in order to attract their attention. This has made them to be more sophisticated in terms of their buying choice. Improved technology and innovations are making consumers to be conscious of the products they are buying, especially aesthetics and other features of the product package. This has made producers to be up and doing due constant changes in consumer choice. This has necessitated constant changes in the product branding and packages. Another major challenge that confronts producers today is the varying needs of different consumer groups. What appeals to a particular group of consumers might not appeal to another consumer group. This makes producers to vary their packaging elements with its attendant cost implication.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to examine the relationship between branding, packaging and consumer choice of soft drinks in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. Ascertain the relationship between branding on consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. Explore the relationship between packaging and consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Branding: includes brand quality, brand value, brand image, brand awareness level, brand name, trade name, logo, marks used to identifying the brands (Leijerhott, *et al* 2019). Kotler (2016) contends that brands is a name, term, symbol, design or all the above, and is used to distinguish one's products and services from that of the competitors.

Packaging: Packaging is a wrapper or container for a product that serves a number of purposes including protection of the product contents, and promotion (Jennifer, 2018). Kotler and Keller, (2016) defined packaging as activities of designing and producing the container for a product. Packaging seems to be one of the most important factors in consumer choice and purchasing decisions made at the point of sales (Prendergast & Pitt, 2016).

Consumer Choice

Customer choice refers as ability and willingness of customer to make decision of what to buy or not to buy any particular point in time. Meanwhile, most times business environmental conditions matter a lot within or outside the organization (Nebo & Onyeke, 2021).

Conceptual Framework

In this section, the researcher developed a conceptual framework depicting the relationship between branding, packaging and consumer choice of soft drinks in Enugu State, Nigeria. As a result, the researcher's conceptual framework was formulated based on these consistent strategies; meanwhile, it was presented below.

Figure 2.1 Proposed modified conceptual model of relationship between branding, packaging and consumers' choice.

Theoretical Framework

Products Attribute Theory

The demand for consumer goods satisfies relatively few simple needs such as food, shelter, and entertainment. These demands are met through the production of various goods and services. Thus, basic human needs can be satisfied through many combinations of materials and technologies. Many goods produced in an advanced economy meet similar needs; consumers apparently select only a few goods on the basis of their price and different qualities or attributes. The traditional analysis of consumer demand deals with consumer choice under budget constraints in which preference ordering is used to maximize utility when price changes. This kind of analysis provides no way for using information about the properties of goods. Lancaster (2017) proposed an

alternative theoretical approach based on the principle that all goods possess characteristics or attributes that are demanded by the consumers, not the goods themselves. For example, consumers do not demand powder detergent in itself, but rather the added value and fragrance in the powder detergent product.

Lancaster stated that traditional analysis cannot predict how demand will be affected by a specified change in one or more properties of a good or how a new good fits into preference patterns over existing goods. Moreover, changes in the characteristics of a good imply a new preference pattern. Consequently, “we must throw away any information derived from observing behavior in the previous situation and begin again from scratch” (Lancaster 2017). In the Lancaster model of consumer demand, the concept of product attributes enters into the demand functions. The theoretical model of demand is based upon estimates of these attributes rather than simply the products themselves.

Empirical Review

Uford and Etim (2018) evaluated the effect of product attributes on consumers' attitude towards made-in-Nigeria textiles in South-South Zone of Nigeria. It examined the effect of product quality and brand value (classified as intrinsic variables of product attributes) on consumers' attitude towards made-in-Nigeria textiles in the south-south zone of Nigeria. A survey design was used in gathering the needed data for this study. The results revealed that there is a significant relationship between product quality, brand value and consumers' attitude towards made-in-Nigeria textiles.

Onyeagwara, Agu and Aja (2019) examined predictors of consumers' choice of buying outlets in Imo and Abia States, Nigeria. The aim of the study was to examine the predictors of consumer's choice of buying outlets in Nigeria. Findings revealed that the three predictors (product, outlet and demographic attributes) are significant predictors of choice of buying outlets by consumers. Further analysis however showed that parking space and price which are variables under outlet and product attributes respectively are not significant predictors of choice of shopping outlet.

Danish, Ali, Ahmad and Zahid (2019) analyzed the influencing factors on choice behavior regarding green electronic products: based on the green perceived value model. The objective of the study was to analyse the influencing factors on choice behavior regarding green electronic products. The results of variance-based structural equation modeling (SEM) (partial least squares (PLS)-SEM) suggested that functional value price, quality, social value identity, responsibility, emotional value, and conditional value positively and significantly influence the consumer choice behavior regarding green electronics.

Domie (2019) study was on assessing the factors influencing consumer switch from local to imported products in Ghana. Both qualitative and quantitative method was employed in attempt to gain an understanding of the research problems. A sample including 100 randomly selected consumers were surveyed using a structured questionnaire and Skype to telephone interview Kasapreko management in the capital of Ghana-Accra. The findings of this study suggest that country of origin is more important than product attributes and other price factors.

Enayet (2019) investigated on the relationship between brand image and each of the preference measures utilized in the study. This finding should be viewed with caution, since the products used in the study were non-durable products. Finally, the measurement and management of brand image have become top priority marketing issues in recent years, as evidenced by the growing literature on the subject. Most articles automatically assume that brand image has an impact on a brand's performance.

Ogbulie, Nwankwo and Egele (2019) investigated the influence of product attributes on consumers purchase decisions on malt drink in Enugu State, Nigeria. Survey research method was employed by administering questionnaire on a sample size of 323 consumers of malt drinks in Enugu determined through convenience sampling method. Cronbatch's alpha coefficient was used to test reliability of the research instrument while regression and Pearson Correlation were used for the analysis. The findings revealed that brand name, attractive packaging and celebrity endorsement significantly influence purchase decision making on Malt drinks.

Popovic, Bossink and Vandersijde (2019) undercooked a review of factors influencing consumers' decision to purchase food in environmentally friendly packaging: what do we know and where do we go from here? To review the extant research on the factors influencing consumers' decision to purchase food in environmentally friendly packaging, we employed a systematic literature review methodology. The review revealed that, although the extant research is growing, it is very limited in terms of the theories utilized to explain consumer purchasing behavior and in the range of the tested predictors of consumers' purchasing of foods in environmentally friendly packaging.

Appu, Bhavana, Parag and Arpan (2024) examined impact of pricing and packaging on consumer buying behavior in Nigeria. The main purpose of the study was to measure the impact of multiple pricing strategy on channel selection by consumers, to measure the satisfaction level of consumers while shopping on multiple channels at multiple prices and to measure influence of consumer shopping orientation on cross channel usage. Product pricing was found to have a statistically significant association with the buyer decision process. Both full and partial mediation were found when satisfaction was used as a mediating variable between pricing and packaging. Findings show that product managers can influence consumers' buying behavior using a combination of pricing and packaging strategies.

Tu, Khairun and Mustaffa (2024) investigated the influence of packaging design on consumer purchasing decisions in China. This research endeavors to unravel the intricate relationship between packaging design and consumer behavior in the context of Northeastern cereal agricultural products. Focusing on the vibrant region of Songyuan, Jilin, China, the study employs a multi-method approach encompassing fieldwork observations, content analysis, and consumer surveys. The findings reveal four distinct models of packaging design, each resonating differently with consumers.

Gap in Empirical Review

This study hopes to breach some of those gaps. Finally, the review of extant literature reveals a large number of studies examining branding, packaging and customers choice in developing countries, including Nigeria. Kheng, Mahamad, Ramayah and Rahim (2010) in their study the findings showed that improvement in product attribute can enhance customer choice. However, previous study ends early 2019 but this present study captured the entire 2024. As can be seen from the above, most studies carried out in this area were done outside Nigeria except few. Moreover, they all were carried out in other sectors of the economy apart from soft drinks establishment. It is this gap that this study seeks to fill.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the survey design. This study was carried out in Enugu State metropolis. Two soft drinks products in Enugu State metropolis were studied namely coco cola and 7up. The consumers of these two soft drinks were covered in this study. The study made use of primary source of data. Cochran's formula for unknown population was applied to determine the sample size of 384. Questionnaire was employed as the instrument of data collection. The data generated were analyzed using correlation analysis.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant positive relationship between branding and consumer’s choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria.

H_{a1}: There is significant positive relationship between branding and consumer’s choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the sign of the coefficient is negative and probability value < 0.05. Otherwise, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate accordingly.

Table 1 Correlation Analysis

Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	Branding	Consumers’ Choice
Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 369	.520** .000 369
Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.459** .000 369	1 369

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 provides the correlation coefficient between branding and consumer’s choice. The results indicated that branding have a strong positive relationship with consumer’s choice. This means that branding has a high correlation output with consumer’s choice of soft drinks as provided by the respective correlation coefficients of first rows $r=.520$ (sig .000< 0.05), Thus we accept alternate hypothesis of H_{a1} which postulated that there was a strong positive relationship between branding and consumer’s choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Packaging has no positive relationship between on consumer’s choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria.

H_{a2}: Packaging has positive relationship on consumer’s choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the sign of the coefficient is negative and probability value < 0.05. Otherwise, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate accordingly.

Table 2 Correlation Analysis

Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	Packaging	Consumers’ Choice
Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 369	.420** .000 369
Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.419** .000 369	1 369

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 provides the correlation coefficient between packaging and consumer's choice. The results indicated that packaging have a strong positive relationship with consumer's choice. This means that packaging has a high correlation output with consumer's choice of soft drinks as provided by the respective correlation coefficients of first rows $r=.420$ ($\text{sig} .000 < 0.05$), Thus we accept alternate hypothesis of H_{a1} which postulated that there was a strong positive relationship between packaging and consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

After data analysis and test of hypotheses, the following findings were stated below;

1. Branding had a positive significant relationship on consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria ($r=.520$, $p_v = .000 < 0.05$).
2. Packaging had a positive significant relationship on consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria ($r=.420$, $p_v = .000 < 0.05$).

Conclusion

Based on summary of findings, the researcher concluded that branding and packaging had a positive significant relationship on consumer's choice of soft drinks in Enugu State metropolis, Nigeria.

Recommendations

In the light of study findings, the following recommendations were made;

1. Manufacturers of soft drinks should ensure that their brands have good image, quality, value for money and identity within the market.
2. Soft drinks manufacturers should ensure that packaging materials, colours, designs, sizes and printed information are good.

REFERENCES

- Appu, A., Bhavana, R.K., Parag, K., & Arpan, S. (2024). Impact of pricing and packaging on consumer buying behavior: a study of its employees in India. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, 28(1), 1-13.
- Damish, N. J., Ali, J. R., Ahmad, M. A. & Zahid, D. (2019). Instrument development and evaluation for measuring USA apparel product design attributes. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, 9(1), 54-70.
- Domie, R. J. (2019). A descriptive model of consumer information search behavior. *Marketing Science*, 1(1), 93-121.
- Enayet, B.N. (2019). A factor analysis of some qualitative attributes of coffee. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 5(3), 35-38.
- Kheng, N. & Gill, H. K. (2010). Consumer evaluations of beautification products: effects of extrinsic cues. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*. 11(2), 89–104
- Kolter, P (2016). When does choice reveal preference? Moderators of Heuristic Versus Goal Base Choice, *Journal of Consumer Research*, 36(3), 137-147

- Lancaster, Y. (2017). The long-term impact of loyalty programs on consumer purchase behavior and loyalty. *Journal of Marketing*, 71(4), 19-35.
- Legerhott, A & Kapferer, K. (2019). Customer loyalty: towards an integrated framework. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 22(2), 99-113
- Nebo, G.N & Onyeke, J.K (2021). *Principles of modern marketing*, first published, Altim Print. Enugu
- Ogbulie, A., Nwankwo, C. & Egele, A. (2019). Influence of product attributes on consumers purchase decisions on malt drink in Enugu State, Nigeria. *American International Journal of Business Management*, 2(12), 18-27.
- Onyeagwara, C. A., Agu, G. A & Aja, E. E. (2019). Predictors of consumers' choice of buying outlets in Imo and Abia States, Nigeria. *Archives of Business Research*, 7(SP), 34-48.
- Popovic, M., Bossink, K., Vandersijde, H., Karumba, A & Ngigi, C (2018). *How brands succeed online*. Cambridge, MA, USA: Forrester: Business View Best Practices
- Prendeagast, D., Johansson, H., Gidlot, J & Wallin, M. (2016). Generalizations regarding the growth and decline of manufacturer and store brands. *J. retail consum. Ser*, 21(5) 725-734
- Tu, L., Khairun, N & Mustaffa, H (2024). Investigating the influence of packaging design on consumer purchasing decisions: a study of northeastern cereal agricultural products in Jilin, China, *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14(8), 2494-2505
- Uford, A & Etim, C (2018). Play, flow, and the online search experience, *Journal of Consumer Research*, 31(2), 324-32.